

European Research Council
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**Religion, Region, Language and the State
ERC SYNERGY PROJECT ASIA 609823
Project workshops 2014-2016**

This document provides a record of the Project Workshops organised under the leadership of Dr Nathan Hill (SOAS) during project period 1 (months 1 – 18, September 2014 to February 2016). As a rule, workshops have been held monthly except in the summer break (July and August).

September 2014 – Research hub set-up and recruitment; no workshop.

October 2014

Religion, Region, Language and the State in Asia

Dr Nathan W. Hill (SOAS, University of London), Dr Sam van Schaik (British Library), and Dr Michael Willis (British Museum)

Date: 14 October 2014 Time: 2:00 PM
Finishes: 14 October 2014 Time: 7:00 PM
Venue: 21 Russell Square Room: MBI Al Jaber Room

This is the first workshop of the new European Research Council project. An introduction to the project, which will run for six years, will be presented by Dr Nathan Hill (SOAS), Sam van Schaik (British Library) and Michael Willis (British Museum).

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November 2014

The Waking and Sleeping of Lord Vishnu: A Seasonal Festival and the Archaeology of Royal Ritual

Dr Michael Willis (British Museum)

Date: 11 November 2014 Time: 2:00 PM
Finishes: 11 November 2014 Time: 7:00 PM
Venue: 21/22 Russell Square Room: MBI Al Jaber Building

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December 2014*Bailang and the Burmish Languages*

Dr Nathan W. Hill (SOAS, University of London)

Date: 16 December 2014 Time: 2:00 PM
Finishes: 16 December 2014 Time: 7:00 PM
Venue: 21 Russell Square Room: MBI Al Jaber Room

Bailang is a Tibeto-Burman language preserved only in the 'Songs of Bailang' (白狼歌) in the Chinese historical text, the 後漢書 Hòu Hànrshū (58-75 C.E.). This paper attempts to gain a better understanding of the Bailang language and its presumed relationship to the Lolo-Burmese languages, by employing recent progress both in Chinese and Burmese historical phonology.

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January 2015*Gupta Numismatics*

Robert Bracey (British Museum)

Date: 13 January 2015 Time: 2:00 PM
Finishes: 13 January 2015 Time: 5:00 PM
Venue: 21/22 Russell Square Room: MBI Al Jaber Room

The presentation will explore what numismatics can offer to questions of general historical interest. It will introduce the reasoning that underpins numismatic research and what the evidence can, and cannot, tell us about economic, political, and social history. This will be done primarily by exploring the collection of Gupta coins at the British Museum.

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February 2015*Sanskrit Manuscripts from Central Asia in the British Library: New Research and Reflections*

Dr Sam van Schaik (British Library)

Date: 10 February 2015 Time: 2:00 PM
Finishes: 10 February 2015 Time: 5:00 PM
Venue: 21/22 Russell Square Room: MBI Al Jaber Room

The Central Asian trade routes known as 'the Silk Road' were of fundamental importance in the spread of Buddhism outside of India. Manuscripts found in archaeological sites along the Silk Road are among the oldest surviving records of

Buddhism. This talk is on the Sanskrit manuscripts from Central Asia, focussing on those kept in the British Library, with reference to the other major collection at the State Library in Berlin. The discovery of the manuscripts, the range of texts they contain, and recent research on them will be summarised, and what they reveal about general historical trends in the transmission of Buddhism will be discussed.

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March 2015

A Chinese traveller on the way to India

Dr Imre Galambos (Cambridge)

Date: 10 March 2015 Time: 2:00 PM
Finishes: 10 March 2015 Time: 5:00 PM
Venue: 21/22 Russell Square Room: MBI Al Jaber Room

Medieval Chinese monks saw India as the land from where Buddhism spread to China. Many monks made the lengthy journey to visit the holy sites associated with the Buddha in search of the dharma, relics and scriptures. The pilgrimage movement generated a substantial body of travel literature which describes not only the final destination but also the road leading there. Among the rare archaeological sources related to these pilgrimages is a scroll from Dunhuang, which was carried by a Chinese monk in the 960s when he passed through Amdo and the Hexi corridor on the way to India. This is a composite manuscript glued together from separate pieces of manuscripts with texts written in Chinese, Tibetan and Sanskrit. The manuscript is a unique material witness of the early Song pilgrimage movement known to us from traditional histories and provides evidence of the complex linguistic situation that existed in this region.

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April 2015

How old is the legend of Aśoka? The growth of Buddhist narratives of kingship in Late Antiquity

Dr Antonello Palumbo (SOAS, University of London)

Date: 14 April 2015 Time: 2:00 PM
Finishes: 14 April 2015 Time: 5:00 PM
Venue: 21/22 Russell Square Room: MBI Al Jaber Room

The figure of the pious king Aśoka has loomed over the modern construction of the history of Buddhism ever since the pioneering efforts of Eugène Burnouf in the early 19th century. However, the monarch of the Maurya inscriptions and its legendary counterpart in the Pāli and Sanskrit traditions have not always been clearly distinguished. Scholars have often been willing to read one into the other, under the more or less tacit assumption that the legend has firm roots in history, and goes back in its core to a very early period. This talk will reassess the historical growth of the

narratives on Aśoka, culminating in the redaction of the Sanskrit Aśoka-avadāna and its Chinese translations; it will suggest that stories about the Maurya monarch were considerably expanded at the beginning of the Gupta period, through the absorption and adaptation of originally independent narrative modules, and responding to the agenda of a politically ambitious Buddhist clergy. This shift will be finally discussed as part of a broader phenomenon across the boundaries of the Old World, the rise of 'religion' and its challenge to the State in Late Antiquity.

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May 2015

Archaeology of early Burma: Results from recent excavations
Prof Janice Stargardt (Cambridge)

Date: 12 May 2015 Time: 2:00 PM
Finishes: 12 May 2015 Time: 5:00 PM
Venue: 21/22 Russell Square Room: MBI Al Jaber Room

From late December 2014 to the end of February 2015 Janice Stargardt, with a joint Cambridge-Field School of Archaeology team, was excavating just outside the southern walls of Sri Ksetra, in Burma. Sri Ksetra was one of the earliest cities in South East Asia and the largest before the emergence of Angkor and Pagan. For the first time in Burma, an ancient habitation site was identified and selectively excavated at the Yahanda mound. Excavations revealed stratified habitational debris, including hardened work surfaces, abundant potsherds, food spills, other compacted organic matter, cooking fires and iron nails. Immediately below rich habitational layers with traces of ancient postholes and pits, the fragmentary brick structure of a former burial terrace was found, containing one cremated burial (so far). Nearby at the Yahanda Gu, a ritual site with a standing monument reconstructed during the Pagan period, a sequence of brick platforms belonging to earlier phases of ritual buildings on that site was exposed, while below them were found dense layers of potsherds and iron nails. Preliminary interpretations will be discussed in the lecture. Both sites are unfinished but work so far will provide objective dates for major phases of activity at both sites and lay the foundations for the first ceramic typologies and chronologies of the first millennium at Sri Ksetra.

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June 2015

Trade of all sorts: The spread of early Śaivism along an ancient caravan route in western India
Prof Hans T. Bakker (British Museum)

Date: 9 June 2015 Time: 2:00 PM
Finishes: 9 June 2015 Time: 5:00 PM
Venue: 21/22 Russell Square Room: MBI Al Jaber Room

The early centuries of the Common Era saw the rise of organised Śaivism, known as Pāśupata, in the country between the Mahī and Narmadā Rivers in southern Gujarat. According to the Pāśupata tradition, Śiva incarnated in a place called Kārohaṇa, identified with the modern village of Karvan, 20 km south of Baroda. This archaeological site is located on the ancient road that connected the port of Bharukaccha (Broach) at the mouth of the Narmadā River with the capital of Western Malwa, Ujjayanī (Ujjain).

The original Skandapurāṇa, an early Śaiva text that was composed between 550 and 650 CE, seems to record the northward movement of the Pāśupata religion, when it mentions the places where the incarnation of the Lord subsequently initiated his four disciples: Ujjayanī, Jambumārga, Mathurā, and Kānyakubja (Kanauj). The route between those places corresponds broadly with the caravan trail that connected the seaport of Broach with the Gangā-Yamunā Doāb during the fourth to six centuries. The correlation between the spread of the Pāśupata movement and the major trade routes of western India will be examined.

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July 2015 – No Workshop

August 2015 – No Workshop

September 2015

Buddhist Rituals in the Gupta Era

Dr Gergely Hidas (British Museum)

Date: 8 September 2015

Time: 2:00 PM

Finishes: 8 September 2015

Time: 5:00 PM

Venue: 21/22 Russell Square

Room: MBI Al Jaber Room

This paper explores ritual activities of the Buddhist Sangha around the middle of the first millennium. The majority of sources which provide information on these belongs to dhāraṇī literature, a genre centred around magical spells and related ritual manuals composed in Sanskrit. Such Buddhist incantation traditions can be traced back to at least the beginning of the Common Era and they appear to have rapidly earned a prominent position in the religious landscape of South Asia and beyond. The main focus of these scriptures is protection and healing and it is notable how these practices are often linked to royal power where more grand-scale rituals like the defence of the state or magical weather control for agriculture are introduced.

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October 2015

The Teachings of the Śivadharma

Prof Peter Bisschop (Leiden)

Date: 13 October 2015

Time: 2:00 PM

Finishes: 13 October 2015 Time: 5:00 PM
Venue: 21/22 Russell Square Room: MBI Al Jaber Room

The Śivadharma text corpus gives rules and regulations for the worship of Śiva. The corpus addresses the community of lay worshippers, among whom the king is prominent. The two earliest and most widespread texts belonging to the Śivadharma are the Śivadharmaśāstra and the Śivadharmottara. These works have been long neglected but they are rich resources for studying the formation and development of early Śaivism. This paper will introduce the various texts and manuscripts of the corpus, assess the state of the field, and focus in particular on chapter 6 of the Śivadharmaśāstra, which consists of an elaborate mantra invoking a plethora of gods, all dependent on the great god Śiva. A study of the names and iconographies of the various gods can help in contextualising and dating this anonymous piece of early Śaiva literature.

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November 2015

Indic Epigraphy in a Digital World
Dr Dániel Balogh (British Museum)

Date: 10 November 2015 Time: 2:00 PM
Finishes: 10 November 2015 Time: 5:00 PM
Venue: 21/22 Russell Square Room: MBI Al Jaber Room

This presentation will examine the computer-based tools that are currently available for the study and understanding of ancient South Asian inscriptions in Sanskrit and Prakrit. A number of databases have been compiled over the last decade, and the strengths and weaknesses of these will be presented and discussed. Some recent projects with a focus other than South Asia—such as the Aphrodisias Project at King's College, London—will also be noted, emphasising features that should be emulated (e.g. the use of Unicode and the EpiDoc markup convention) as well as points where existing solutions will need to be adapted to the characteristics of Indic languages or South Asian scripts. Other relevant computational tools will also be noted, in particular Harry Falk's Indoskript, pointing out the technological changes that are needed to expand and upgrade this resource. The presentation is designed to provide a basis for a planning session about the IT needs of the ERC project and the configuration of its online platform.

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December 2015

Local and Translocal Dimensions in the Making of Theravāda Buddhism
Dr Sven Bretfeld (NTNU Trondheim)

Date: 8 December 2015 Time: 2:00 PM
Finishes: 8 December 2015 Time: 5:00 PM

Venue: 21/22 Russell Square Room: MBI Al Jaber Room

In the Gupta Age a Buddhist lineage appeared on the “international” Buddhist stage calling itself Theriya or (less frequently) Theravāda Nikāya. In its self-descriptions this Sri Lanka-based group claimed to be of superior decent in terms of originality and trustfulness to the dhammavinaya of the Buddha. Apparently around the same time this group started to promote the use of what they called Māgadhi—a language of unclear origin, today known as Pāli—as the preferred language of Buddhist scholarship. In the concert of Buddhist group-identities this lineage—or at least parts of it—tried to play the role of conservative preservers of the Buddha’s original teaching and language. As such it set itself into contrast with the established, partly supra-regionally active and reputed monastic “schools” (nikāya) as well as with the rising Mahāyāna movement. With the Dīpavamsa (4th cent.) and, even more so, with the Mahāvamsa (5th/6th cent.) and the Nikāyasamgrahaya (13th cent.) this lineage formulated a claim of uniqueness within the Buddhist World as the last representative of “true Buddhism.” Instead of denoting an ancient or non-Mahāyāna form of Buddhism, the term Theravāda must be understood as a positioning concept, coined and promoted—rather lately—as an authenticity claim in a specific historical context of inner-Buddhist diversity and cross-cultural encounter. In my paper I am going to analyse the local and translocal dimensions of this discourse.

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January 2016

Mahasthan, the easternmost Indian city

Dr Vincent Lefèvre (CNRS)

Date: 12 January 2016 Time: 2:00 PM
Finishes: 12 January 2016 Time: 5:00 PM
Venue: 21/22 Russell Square Room: T102

Identified by Alexander Cunningham as the ancient Pundranagara or the capital of Pundravardhana, Mahasthan (or Mahasthangarh), in today's Bangladesh, was most probably founded in the late 4th century BCE in a previously uninhabited land, perhaps as a result of the Mauryan expansion. With some variations through time, the city flourished until the end of the 'Pala-Sena' period, even though the site shows also some remains from the Muslim period. It is rare in India that a city can be explored across such a long time span. Since 1993, joint Bangladeshi-French excavations have been conducted in Mahasthan. This research enables us to give a more precise chronological framework for the city. Whereas the epigraphical record from the Gupta period presents Pundravardhana as an important part of the 'Empire', Gupta remains are conspicuously rare at Mahasthan, at least in the present state of the excavations. Conversely, the post-Gupta period seems to be a busy one in the history of the site. This presentation will seek to introduce the new data given by archaeological research and discuss them in the light of the context and the (few) written records.

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February 2016

The reflection of India in early Tibetan historiography: a comparative approach

Dr Lewis Doney (British Museum)

Date: 9 February 2016 Time: 2:00 PM

Finishes: 9 February 2016 Time: 5:00 PM

Venue: 21/22 Russell Square Room: T102

Tibet has maintained literary contact with South Asia since its imperial period (c.600–850 CE). These ties were strengthened with the influx of Buddhism into the country from this period onwards. Over the next few centuries, many Indic literary traditions were adapted and incorporated into Tibetan culture at all levels. This talk will focus on the birth and growth of Tibetan Buddhist historiography as a literary genre in particular. Special attention will be given to the Testimony of Ba tradition, which narrates the introduction of Buddhism to Tibet from India and China, and biographies of the eighth-century Indic tantric master, Padmasambhava. Recently discovered sources of these works enable a new assessment of the changing perception of South Asia, as distinct from other regions, expressed in early Tibetan Buddhist life-writing. This discussion will take place within a comparative framework that compares dynamics in early Tibetan Buddhist historiography with some of those found in such countries as Sri Lanka and China.

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